

Approved Proposals of the 2nd FAIRagro Use Case Call 2025

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Introduction

FAIRagro is a community-driven initiative within the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). Our mission is to establish an interoperable and scalable research data infrastructure and services that advances FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) research data management (RDM) and to support the cultural change towards collaborative RDM practices. FAIRagro aims to foster highly interdisciplinary and multiscale research in agroecosystem-related sciences, a field of immense societal relevance.

Our goal is to support agricultural scientists with FAIR RDM by building infrastructures and services tailored to their needs. Through this effort, we strive to make FAIR practices the norm, increasing openness and integrity of research. We aim to empower researchers to share their work transparently and ensure data is discoverable and (re)usable across disciplines. As part of the broader NFDI mission, FAIRagro is committed to building a scientific future where FAIR data practices are recognized, rewarded, and integrated into innovative research.

For the years 2024-2026 we provide funds for new, community driven Use Case Pilots and Projects (UCs). The funds are allocated via two Calls in 2024 and 2025. UCs are practical examples that describe and address specific challenges in RDM within agricultural sciences as well as develop and test potential solutions. They enable FAIRagro to collaboratively tackle the spatial, subject and technical diversity of agricultural data.

The second UC call took place between January June and March 2025. 11 UC applications with running times up to 18 months were submitted. Two UC applications were approved by reviewers from the FAIRagro Community Advisory Board and the FAIRagro Steering Committee.

We here provide the approved UC applications including working plans, running times, connections to the FAIRagro Task Areas, measures and deliverables:

- 1 Agri-Gaia meets DataHUB: Connecting Technologies & Communities via a Potato Virus Dataset FAIRification “AgDaFAIR” by H. Tapken and T. Mühlhaus (p. 3-13)
- 2 Unlocking Multifunctional Insights with Near-Surface Geophysical Data Harmonization in Agriculture “MUFUDAT.agrio” by U. Werban and C. Schütze (p.14-27)

The new UCs were integrated to the FAIRagro Task Area TA1 and are now part of the newly established Measure 1.13 (Use Case 13, AgDaFAIR, start July 2025) and Measure 1.14 (Use Case 14 MUFUDAT.agrio, start October 2025). Due to necessary budget cuts, a minor adjustment to the durations and work programs are possible.

The work programs of the approved proposals are extensions to the FAIRagro Proposal DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.836688

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1 Agri-Gaia meets DataHUB: Connecting Technologies & Communities via a Potato Virus Dataset FAIRification “AgDaFAIR”

Applicants: **Prof. Dr. -Ing Heiko Tapken** (Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences, HSOS) and **Prof. Dr. Timo Mühlhaus** (University of Kaiserslautern, RPTU)

Associated Partner: Bundesverband Deutscher Pflanzenzüchter e.V.; Dr. Steffen Kawelke (Gemeinschaft zur Förderung von Pflanzeninnovation e. V., GFPI); Matthias Hempe (EuroPlant Pflanzenzucht GmbH)

Running time: 18 months, July 2025-Dec 2026

Keywords: FAIR potato virus dataset, (technical and semantical) interoperability, data spaces, AI-Development, ARC DataHUB

UC description and scientific details

Short UC summary (Abstract)

This UC Project addresses two objectives: First: provide and disseminate a FAIR-annotated image dataset on potato viruses to the community with the goal of enabling publicly usable insights (e.g. using AI). Second: Create seamless interoperability between the Agri-Gaia AI-development platform (Agri-Gaia) with the ARC DataHUB (DataHUB) a FAIR research data management and publication platform.

The idea of creating, disseminating and analyzing a potato virus data set was brought to RPTU and HSOS by the GFPI and EuroPlant. The dataset will be used to showcase semantical and technical interoperability. This integration will facilitate seamless interaction and model training on data encapsulated as ARCs, while also providing a FAIR description of the AI workflow via the ARC RO Crate workflow profile.

Agri-Gaia supports the whole AI-lifecycle. Platforms may be used at user’s premise or by using a managed cloud-installation. Using the Eclipse Dataspace Components, platforms can be combined into one data space or connected to other data spaces. Each platform instance provides an OpenAPI based connector to connect external software services or integrate public base data. The results are integrated into the Agri-Gaia data management system.

ARC DataHUB enables users to progressively transform their data into FAIR digital objects and publish them in line with the evolving FAIR-by-design principle. Acting as a technological middleware, the DataHUB integrates large datasets from diverse providers within the FAIRagro consortium and offers a suite of user-friendly tools for ARC-based research data management and evolution. Additionally, it establishes connections with other consortia such as DataPLANT, Microbiota, and Biodiversity.

UC concept and objectives

Figure 1: Overall concept

The idea for this UC project was brought to us by GFPi and EuroPlant. One request was to enable the provision of an annotated potato virus dataset under FAIR principles. The dataset will be created, annotated and made available in the project free of charge by Europlant. The associated partners also hope that data analysts will become aware of the dataset. AI developers should be able to use this dataset to develop new AI models for the detection and classification of potato viruses from the resulting annotated image dataset using computer vision. These AI models and further information about the dataset should then be made available to the community.

This led to the project idea of enabling bidirectional interoperability at the data and metadata level between DataHUB and Agri-Gaia and thus also being able to provide the analysis results under FAIR principles.

Successful agricultural research and application rely on the effortless training and deployment of AI based models on real-world data—eliminating technical barriers for users. To this end, our project integrates the Agri-Gaia technology platform with the ARC DataHUB, a FAIR research data management and publication platform, to drive innovation in agricultural research.

Our overall use case centers on the production of a well-annotated FAIR digital object in the form of an ARC developed collaboratively with the agricultural community. Specifically, we will focus on a potato virus dataset to demonstrate the application of AI-based objects using the Agri-Gaia platform. This collaborative process leverages the DataHUB platform to engage community input while technically bridging the gap between the DataHUB metadata platform and the Agri-Gaia platform.

The key objectives of our project are to:

- Facilitate User-Friendly AI Integration: Enable easy training, management, inference and deployment of AI models on authentic agricultural FAIR data objects without imposing technical burdens (in a code/no-code manner).
- Enhance FAIRness and Interoperability: Create well-annotated, FAIR digital objects in the form of ARC RO Crates and support their semantic interoperability and bidirectional technical integration between platforms.
- Leverage Existing Integration Infrastructure: The ARC DataHUB, already serving as middleware in FAIRagro and actively used by DataPLANT (with extensions to NFDI4BioIMAGING and NFDI4Biodiversity), inherently unifies data efforts from multiple NFDI initiatives. Multiple Agri-Gaia platforms may be connected by Eclipse Dataspace Components
- to build a data space. Connections to various other DS-initiatives (e. g. AgIN, IDSA, Pontus-X, AgriFoodTEF) are work in progress and will link FAIRagro to these technologies. In addition, Agri-Gaia supports service and data connectors using OpenAPI. Our goal is to seamlessly connect both infrastructures and enable robust, community-driven data publication without additional integration overhead.
- Demonstrate End-to-End Workflow: Validate the integration through a complete workflow— from research data aggregation to AI model application—using the potato virus dataset as a tangible proof of concept.

By achieving these objectives, our project will not only remove technical barriers for end users but also establish a scalable, FAIR-by-design ecosystem that paves the way for advanced AI research and application in agriculture.

Added expertise, scientific background, and preliminary work

HSOS projects relevant to the AgDaFAIR

- AgriFoodTEF
- AgriDataspace
- Agri-Gaia
- SDSD
- FarmSPT

Prof. Tapken works in multiple standardization committees and is a member of the expert group on AI security of the BSI. Data space involvements include

- AgIN
- EDC
- IDSA
- Pontus-X
- Gaia-X

RPTU serves as the primary developer and implementer of the DataHUB and ARC concept, driving innovation and ensuring robust, FAIR-compliant data integration and management.

GFPi:

- Organization dedicated to supporting innovation in plant breeding and research
- Research projects with HSOS:
 - Senselgo
 - Standards4DroPhe
 - Crop Virus Scan

Europlant:

- Well-known potato breeding company
- Provider of potato virus dataset

Publications

PLANTDataHUB: a collaborative platform for continuous FAIR data sharing in plant research. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.16474>

Immutable yet evolving: ARCs for permanent sharing in the research data-time continuum. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11588/heibooks.979.c13751>

Metadata Management and Asset Exchange in the Agricultural Data Ecosystem of the Project Agri-Gaia
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13222-023-00444-3>

Accelerating the AI lifecycle with the AgriGaia-Plattform (Published in: <https://www.vdi-nachrichten.com/shop/land-technik-2024/>, Page 63)

KI-basiertes Computer-Vision-System zur Qualitäts- und Größenbestimmung von Kartoffeln (43. GIL-Jahrestagung, Resiliente Agri-Food-Systeme. Bonn: Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V.. PISSN: 1617-5468. ISBN: 978-3-88579-724-1. pp. 219-230)

Dezentrale Plattformen im Agri-Gaia Ökosystem: Entwicklung und Management landwirtschaftlicher Daten und KI-Lösungen (Poster at GIL, Accessable: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368849116_Dezentrale_Plattformen_im_Agri_Gaia_Okosystem_Entwicklung_und_Management_landwirtschaftlicher_Daten_und_KI_Losungen)

Involvement disciplines, institutions and cooperation with other initiatives/ projects

The allocation of the involved (associated) partners to the work steps can be found in the work plan. All (associated) partners are networked in many ways and serve as a connecting link to FAIRagro in the following institutions.

Scientific Disciplines

- Agricultural research
- Fundamental plant research
- AI research

Institutions

- Agri-Gaia: DKE agrirouter, Agrotech Valley Forum e.V., Friends of Digital Farming e.V., VDMA, VDI/TC 347

(Agricultural) Research Communities, Initiatives and Projects

- Agri-Gaia: Pontus-X
- Europlant
- Gemeinschaft zur Förderung von Pflanzeninnovation e. V.

(Inter-)national RDM Initiatives

- NFDI and DataPLANT
- DataHUB user community (NFDI4BioIMAGING , NFDI4Biodiversity, CPLAS) • AgriDataSpace, AEF AgIn,
- EDC, Pontus-x, Gaia-x, Industrial Dataspace Association

UC - RDM specifications and FAIRagro connection

UC inventory and specification of characteristics relevant for RDM

Category	Description: UC specification and examples
Disciplines	potato growers, data spaces experts, AI developer, plant researchers, data stewards, plant metadata standard developers
Scales	We want to verify the technical solutions by using a dataset consisting of potato plants with various diseases to train a model on this dataset
Data domains	Technical interoperability: generic domains Potato dataset: crop management
Data types	Technical interoperability: Generic, focus on Images Potato dataset: annotated image dataset
File formats	Datasets: open Metadata: JSON-LD
Source data / database / repositories	Dataset provider: EuroPlant GmbH Technical source data provider: ARC DataHUB (FAIRagro middleware)
Processing workflows	Integration on application level (bidirectional interaction between DataHUB and Agri-Gaia ecosystems)
Tools/software	Agri-Gaia Platform (MIT-license)

	Description: UC specification
TRL of UC today	DataHUB (stand-alone): TRL 7 Agri-Gaia (stand-alone): TRL 7 Interoperability between both: TRL 1 Potato Virus DataSet: 2
TRL of UC after completion of UC Project/ Pilot	DataHUB (stand-alone): TRL 7 Agri-Gaia (stand-alone): TRL 7 Interoperability between both: TRL 7 Potato Virus DataSet: 4

RDM practices & FAIRness status quo

The current RDM practices in this Use Case are firmly rooted in a FAIR-by-design approach, utilizing the ARC DataHU-B to transform datasets—such as the potato virus dataset—into fully annotated ARC based FAIR digital objects. This digital framework employs robust standards and metadata models, including the ISA model for multi-level annotation and the Common Workflow Language (CWL) for seamless workflow integration. ARCs serve as de facto RO-Crate implementations, enhanced with Schema.org and BioSchema.org decorations, ensuring data is structured, shareable, replicable, and continuously evolvable with comprehensive metadata, ontologies, and data quality checks. An integrated data publication process further facilitates the assignment and retrieval of persistent identifiers (PIDs).

Moreover, Agri-Gaia enhances these practices by offering secure and interoperable data and model transfer capabilities via the Eclipse Dataspace Connector and GaiaX-compliant software. Combining these two platforms ensures that the FAIR principles are fully integrated and supported across the entire research data management lifecycle.

UC contributions and benefits

FAIRagro Connection through respective TAs and focal points	Short explanation (in bullet points)
<i>TA 3: Standardization, Interoperability & Quality</i>	
Standards for digital resources	Enhancement of the Agri-Gaia Metadata descriptions by introducing ARC RO crate metadata standard
Standards for data management	EDC, ISO/TC 347: data driven agrifood systems, AgIn, Pontus-x, VDI/VDE 3714 (Big Data), AEF data management working group
Data quality annotation and curation	Through the labelling and annotation process on the DataHUB platform the data will be enriched with additional metadata, to enhance findability.
FAIR workflows and FAIR Digital Objects	During the integration into the platform, executed workflows like data annotation or model training will be documented and added into the metadata of the ARC FAIR digital object.
<i>TA 4: Services</i>	
Networked RDI	We will be using the DataHUB as a data infrastructure to receive FAIR digital objects and enhance this DataHUB to be able to also import FAIR digital objects from other sources, for example an Agri-Gaia platform.
Searchable inventory of services and data	Through extensive addition of metadata to objects on the Agri-Gaia platform, the objects will become more searchable.
<i>TA5: Overarching activities</i>	
Internationalisation	ELIXIR, AgriFoodTEF, AEF working group data management
Cross-NFDI networking	FAIRagro, DataPLANT, NFDI4BioIMAGING, and NFDI4Biodiversity

UC requirements

Since the DataHUB is already fully operational as the middleware in FAIRagro (TA 4 M4.2) and is actively used as PLANTDataHUB in DataPLANT, no additional implementation dependencies are required.

UC outcomes and outreach

Expected outcomes and impact

The primary outcomes of this Use Case include transforming the potato virus dataset into a fully annotated ARC-based FAIR digital object, establishing seamless interoperability between the ARC DataHUB and the Agri-Gaia platform, and demonstrating effective AI model training and application on real-world agricultural data. This integration is expected to enhance data discoverability, reproducibility, and scalability, thereby fostering a more collaborative research environment across multiple initiatives.

- Integrated Service: Semantic and technical integration between the FAIRagro middleware and the Agri-Gaia platform
- FAIR and AI actionable dataset: The potato virus dataset as fully annotated ARC-based FAIR digital objects with comprehensive metadata usable by the Agri-Gaia platform

Potential Performance Indicators:

- Dataset FAIRness
- Platform integration and usage
- Active user interactions (counts, download/usage statistics)
- Number of institutions using the potato dataset
- Number of generated AI models

A potential risk affecting the outputs could be difficulties harmonizing metadata formats and data exchange protocols between the ARC DataHUB and Agri-Gaia platforms. However, this risk is expected to be minor since the project team includes platform experts from both systems who can proactively address and resolve any issues that arise.

Outreach & community engagement

FAIR principles are part of the HSOS guideline for research data management (RDM) and the “Regulations for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice at Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences”

HSOS applied for membership of the NFDI e.V. and has a dedicated FDM employee. UC project will:

- establish FAIR RDM as a normative standard at HSOS and enable joint workshops
- spread visibility of FAIRagro and FAIR principles to all research projects at HSOS
- broaden the visibility of FAIRagro in research consortia (AgriFoodTEF, FarmSPT) and standardization (ISO/TC 347, AEF)

RPTU:

- has a leading role in NFDI consortium DataPlant
- is a member of the NFDI consortia: FAIRmat, MatWerk, MarDi, and NFDI4Chem • RPTU participates in the basic service projects IAM4NFDI and TS4NFDI.
- Researcher Support by the Research Data Management Network Rhineland-Palatinate (FDM.RLP).
- Participation in the Rhineland-Palatinate Data Center Alliance creates teaching and research resources.
- A leading role in the AI Alliance Rhineland-Palatinate (in collaboration with JGU Mainz), which consolidates AI research activities in the region.

GFPi/EuroPlant:

- Publish a dataset under the FAIR principles for the first time
- Provide an annotated potato viruses Dataset to the community (shared insights for the community)

Workplan

Actions (Work packages)

#	Action	Responsible Institution	Contributing instit./partner
A1	Preparation and conception: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Getting into API definitions of participating partners ➤ Conception of DataHUB conform Data lineage within Agri-Gaia platform ➤ Definition of needed components for interaction (including APIs) ➤ Definition of components for user interaction (UI) 	HSOS, RPTU	
A2	Data and Transfer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Create common data backlog ➤ Concept for data transfer from DataHUB to Agri-Gaia ➤ Implementation of data lineage within Agri-Gaia ➤ Concept for data transfer from Agri-Gaia to DataHUB 	HSOS, RPTU	GFPi, Europlant
A3	Metadata and Transfer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Create common backlog of metadata including semantic annotations ➤ Definition of Algorithms for the bidirectional conversion of metadata between systems ➤ Implementation of prototype for datatransfer DataHUB to Agri-Gaia ➤ Implementation of prototype for datatransfer from Agri-Gaia to DataHUB 	HSOS, RPTU	
A4	UseCase: Potato Viruses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Creating test dataset ➤ Providing dataset on DataHUB ➤ Transfer of dataset to Agri-Gaia platform ➤ AI assisted Labeling of dataset on Agri Gaia platform ➤ Transfer of annotated dataset to DataHUB ➤ Training of Computer Vision model for virus detection on Agri-Gaia platform ➤ Testing developed AI model in cooperation with AgriFoodTEF ➤ Transfer of Model to DataHUB 	HSOS, RPTU	Europlant
A5	Publish and Share results: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Publishing results ➤ Cooperation with FAIRagro consortium ➤ Community curation and expansion ➤ Contribution on standardization 	HSOS, RPTU	

Milestones

#	Milestone (Name and description)	Action #	Achieved after month x
M1	GfPI, EuroPlant created ARC	2,3,4	6
M2	ARC import- und actionable in Agri-Gaia	1,2,3	10
M3	Model training and resulting model are described by semantics on Agri-Gaia platform	1,2,3,4	14
M4	Model can be transferred back to DataHUB and is findable. Bidirectional Interoperability is established and shown on the potato virus dataset	1,2,3,4	18

Deliverables

#	Deliverable (Name and description)	Action #	Achieved after month x
D1	Publication of dataset (potato plants and viruses) as FAIR digital object	4,5	4
D2	Platform integration and documentation on usage	1,2,3	12
D3	AI-models published in the form of Fair digital objects	1,2,3,4,5	18

2 Unlocking Multifunctional Insights with Near-Surface Geophysical Data Harmonization in Agriculture

Applicants: **Dr. Ulrike Werban** and **Dr. Claudia Schütze** (Helmholtz Zentrum für Umweltforschung, UFZ)

Additional associated partner: Till Sonnemann (Bonn Center for Digital Humanities, Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn); Deutsche Geophysikalische Gesellschaft (DGG); NFDI4Objects; NFDI4Earth; Deutsche Bodenkundliche Gesellschaft (DBG).

Running time: 12 months, 2025/2026

Keywords: Near-surface geophysics, precision agriculture, cross-domain, harmonization, FAIR

UC description and scientific details

Short UC summary (Abstract)

Near-surface geophysical methods are increasingly used in precision farming, providing rapid, cost-effective assessments of soil moisture, texture, and nutrient status. With advancements in sensor-based monitoring, AI-driven analysis, and automated machinery, the volume and complexity of agricultural data will continue to grow. However, these datasets hold value beyond agriculture, offering insights into archaeological features, soil processes, and environmental dynamics. A harmonized, cross-disciplinary framework will maximize their usability across scientific domains. The UC project “MUFUDAT.agrio” aims to enhance the usability of geophysical datasets obtained in precision farming through a structured workflow ensuring harmonization, quality assurance, and long-term accessibility. This workflow will address three key components: data acquisition, processing (including QA/QC), and archiving procedures. A dedicated agricultural pilot site will serve as a testbed and will also provide opportunities for archaeological prospection, allowing for the investigation of potential subsurface features. The project will implement Electromagnetic Induction (EMI), Gamma-Ray Spectroscopy (GRS), and optical spectroscopy as exemplary methods, demonstrating the structured workflow and refining data integration processes. By developing standardized metadata structures and controlled vocabularies, the project will create the basis to facilitate cross-disciplinary collaboration between agriculture, archaeology, and Earth System Sciences, promoting interoperability and long-term data usability. MUFUDAT.agrio forms the first phase of the broader “Multifunctional Data in a Multifunctional Landscape” initiative, a cross-consortium partnership between FAIRagro, NFDI4Objects and NFDI4Earth.

UC concept and objectives

Multifunctional Data in a Multifunctional Landscape: Multi-Purpose Near-Surface Geophysical Prospecting

Fig.1: The UC project “MUFUDAT.agrio” is part of the overarching three-phases concept “**Multifunctional Data in a Multifunctional Landscape**” which is planned to combine the strengths of three NFDI-initiatives (FAIRagro, NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Earth). The overall objective of this approach is to harmonize the cross-domain generation of near-surface geophysical data, fostering data usability across broader user communities, interoperability, and long-term research data management impact (Werban et al., 2025). In the first phase covered by this proposal, the work focuses on the development and implementation of a structured data workflow, including data and metadata fusion, to enhance the cross-discipline reusability of geophysical datasets acquired in precision farming applications.

Precision farming introduces a new level of high-resolution data collection, enabling detailed soil condition mapping and crop growth monitoring on farms based on e.g., geophysical methods, remote sensing techniques, and autonomous robots (among others). As technology advances, the volume, velocity and variety of data generated through precision farming is expected to grow significantly, driven by the increasing adoption of sensor-based monitoring, automated machinery, and AI-driven decision support systems. Farmers' motivation to adopt precision farming methods, despite the associated initial costs, is steadily rising (Webber et al., 2019). This trend is largely influenced by practical experience with the technology, the ability to integrate new systems into existing farm machinery, and growing confidence in the effectiveness of data-driven agricultural strategies.

Near-surface geophysical methods have become increasingly important tools in applied agricultural practices and studies (Garré et al., 2021). The great advantage of “agrogeophysical” methods is their potential rapidity, low cost, and spatial coverage and thus can easily be integrated in precision farming practices both in terms of prospection and monitoring. Agricultural geophysics investigations commonly focus on obtaining information concerning properties, conditions and related processes in soils, whose depths generally do not extend much beyond 2 meters beneath the ground surface. Covered areas can vary widely in scale, from experimental plots (several square meters), to farm fields (several hectares), up to the size of watersheds (several square kilometers).

Beyond their application in agriculture, the near-surface geophysical datasets generated in agricultural investigations often contain valuable information that extends far beyond precision farming and management decisions. These datasets can reveal subsurface anomalies indicative of archaeological remains, such as buried structures, former settlement areas, or ancient land-use modifications. Additionally, they provide critical insights into broader soil processes, including erosion patterns, hydrological dynamics, and long-term soil formation, which are highly relevant to environmental sciences and Earth system research. Consequently, the need for structured data management and standardization will become even more critical in the future. By structuring and archiving these datasets in a harmonized, cross-disciplinary framework, their usability can be maximized across multiple scientific domains. This will expand the research community and foster stronger interdisciplinary collaboration.

The main objective of the UC project is to maximize the usability across multiple scientific domains of near-surface geophysical prospection datasets obtained in precision farming based on the implementation of a structured workflow concept. This workflow will ensure harmonization, quality assurance, and long-term data accessibility, facilitating cross-disciplinary data integration in order to achieve multimodal datasets. The proposed **workflow consists of three key components:**

- 1) Data Acquisition: Establishing standardized protocols for data collection, ensuring consistency in sensors / instruments deployment, measurement procedures, and data

formats. This phase focuses on raw data generation and the documentation with sufficient metadata in a structured manner to enable reproducibility and interoperability.

2) Data Processing: Implementing comprehensive documentation of quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) measures, including the transparent documentation of processing steps and validation procedures. This ensures that processed datasets and data products are traceable and meet high scientific standards.

3) Data Archiving and Publication: Defining best practices for metadata curation, data storage, and accessibility in metadata portals and open repositories. By aligning with FAIR principles, this phase enhances data discoverability, reusability, and long-term availability for applications beyond precision farming.

To establish such a workflow a detailed description of tasks is given in section 5. By integrating these workflow components, the project aims to create a harmonized data framework that supports multi-purpose usability, cross-domain collaboration, and scalable data-driven research (Werban et al., 2025).

Ensuring long-term and cross-discipline reusability requires comprehensive and well-structured metadata, which captures essential details on data acquisition, processing, and contextual factors. Hence, the definition and prioritization of metadata entries is a critical aspect in the development of proposed workflow. Based on previous studies (e.g. Ködel et al., 2022; Schütze & Dietrich, 2025), metadata can be categorized related to (1) observation and measurements, (2) sample and data history, (3) sensors and devices, (4) methods and processing, (5) environmental characteristics (spatial and temporal). Here, we identified different levels of importance: core metadata (essential and mandatory, including fundamental descriptors) and extended metadata (providing crucial contextual and methodological details enhancing the reusability of datasets beyond their original scope). A well-structured metadata framework must strike a balance between compulsory core metadata and additional metadata layers that facilitate comprehensive, cross-domain data integration. To support and enhance metadata provision, the use of controlled vocabularies is essential. These vocabularies ensure consistency, interoperability, and clarity across datasets. As part of this UC project, they will be developed, refined, and continuously updated through a curated process, ensuring their alignment with evolving research needs and cross-domain applicability.

The practical implementation of the UC project to demonstrate FAIR practices will be conducted using an agricultural pilot site, where all involved disciplines—agriculture, archaeology, and Earth System Sciences—can address their discipline-specific research questions. At the same time, the site will serve as a connecting platform for generating a harmonized, cross-disciplinary dataset, reusable beyond individual research domains. One potential site, an agricultural area with a size of approx. 30 ha, is selected in collaboration with the State Office for Heritage Management and Archaeology Saxony-Anhalt. The site under current consideration is of particular interest due to its location along the planned SuedOst

Link DC power corridor in Saxony-Anhalt (section A2, municipality Kabelsketal) and the high potential for neolithic and medieval archaeological features, which require systematic mapping beyond agricultural research questions.

This controlled setting allows for systematic testing and refinement of standardized protocols while ensuring data quality and interoperability. The focus will be laid on geophysical methods that are widely applied in precision farming, particularly Electromagnetic Induction (EMI), Gamma-Ray Spectroscopy (GRS) and optical spectroscopy (e.g., in the NIR range for plant stress and soil characterization), also by including multi-sensor platforms. These techniques provide rapid, high-resolution assessments of soil properties through proxy relationships. By implementing and evaluating the workflow at the pilot site, the project ensures practical applicability while building the foundation for scalable and cross-domain geophysical data integration. Additionally, the structured data generated through this approach will enhance the applicability of AI-driven models, enabling automated pattern recognition, adaptive learning, and predictive analytics for soil characterization and archaeological feature detection.

Added expertise, scientific background, and preliminary work

The Department Monitoring and Exploration Technologies at UFZ has particular expertise in near-surface geophysical methods enabling rapid, large-scale assessment of soil moisture and other soil properties. These methods are actively applied, validated and continuously refined for precision agriculture and digital soil mapping. The resulting datasets were FAIR-aligned processed, archived in public repositories, and often reused beyond the original scope, demonstrating their long-term value. There is an enhanced expertise in comprehensive FAIR data management based on work in initiatives like Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration, as a participant in NFDI4Earth and on the operation of large-scale research infrastructures (TERENO, MOSES). The UFZ is participant in NFDI4Objects and involved in the development of workflows for the processing, evaluation and long-term storage of remote sensing data and geophysical sensor information in geoinformation systems based on FAIR principles (TRAIL 1.2).

Bonn University / Bonn Center for Digital Humanities (associated partner) is co-applicant of the NFDI4Objects consortium and also a partner in TRAIL 1.2.

Publications

Dierke, C., Werban, U. (2013): Relationships between gamma-ray data and soil properties at an agricultural test site, *Geoderma* 199 , 90 - 98 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2012.10.017>

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Involvement disciplines, institutions and cooperation with other initiatives/ projects

The UC project is embedded in an overarching three-phases concept “Multifunctional Data in a Multifunctional Landscape” which is planned to combine the strengths of three NFDI-initiatives: FAIRagro, NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Earth (Werban et al., 2025; see also appendix). UFZ plays a key role in all three initiatives as a participant, contributing its expertise in environmental research, data management, and geophysical methods. The overall objective of this approach is to harmonize the cross-domain generation of near-surface geophysical data, fostering data usability across broader user communities, interoperability, and long-term research data management impact. With the presented concept the authors identify key challenges in multi-purpose geophysical data usage and present a conceptual framework to address these obstacles effectively. Hence, the targeted disciplines and research communities integrated in the Use Case are precision agriculture, near-surface geophysics, archaeology and Earth System Sciences. For that purpose several stakeholders and institutions will be involved with their specific roles, such as:

- NFDI4Objects (Task Area 1, Dr. Matthias Lang) - stakeholder, contribution of perspectives relevant for the archaeological community
- NFDI4Earth (Dr. Jan Bumberger) - stakeholder, contribution of perspectives relevant for the Earth System Sciences community
- Deutsche Geophysikalische Gesellschaft: AK Angewandte Geophysik (Dr. A. Schuck), AK Hydro- und Ingenieurgeophysik (PD Dr. Ernst Niederleithinger) - stakeholder, contribution concerning metadata and data standards in geophysics
- Landesamt für Denkmalpflege und Archäologie Sachsen-Anhalt (Dr. Susanne Friedrich) - stakeholder, contributions to find optimal pilot site with agricultural + archaeological features
- Deutsche Bodenkundliche Gesellschaft: AG Bodensensorik und Pedometrie (Dr. M. Möller) - stakeholder, contribution concerning metadata and data standards in soil sciences
- Leibniz-Institut für Agrartechnik und Bioökonomie e.V. (ATB) Bornim (Asim Khawaja, WetNetBB project) - stakeholder, contribution in terms of wetland agricultural aspects and FAIR data management plans
- FAIRagro Use Case 2 (ZALF et al.) - planned contribution and collaboration concerning cross-disciplinary usability of data products for model-validation
- FAIRagro Use Case 5 PhenoRob (FZ Jülich, Uni Bonn) - planned contribution and collaboration concerning sensor systems metadata and cross-disciplinary usability of data products

UC - RDM specifications and FAIRagro connection

UC inventory and specification of characteristics relevant for RDM

Category	Description: UC specification and examples
Disciplines	Agronomy, Soil science, Geophysics, Archaeology, Data Science and Artificial Intelligence
Scales	plot to landscape (small catchment)
Data domains	near surface geophysical data, soil, yield information
Data types	tabular, images, ...
File formats	csv, json, xml, GeoTiff
Source data / database / repositories	UFZ data investigation portal, PANGAEA, BonaRes Repository
Processing workflows	concept, prototype and testing on pilot site use case
Tools/software	Python, R, RDMO, QGIS, GitLab

	Description: UC specification
TRL of UC today	<p>intra-disciplinary: TRL 3 (recommendations for structured data management in progress)</p> <p>interdisciplinary: TRL 1 (no structured data management, no open and joint use of the data)</p>
TRL of UC after completion of UC Project/ Pilot	<p>intra-disciplinary: TRL 5 (structured data management for different methods validated n at a demo field site)</p> <p>interdisciplinary: TRL 3 (recommendations developed for structured data management)</p>

RDM practices & FAIRness status quo

- UC will enhance the interoperability (I) and reusability (R) of near-surface geophysical data across disciplinary boundaries and develop reusable workflows facilitating comprehensive data integration across precision agricultural, archaeological and Earth System Sciences applications.
- Data acquisition, processing, and publication will follow a structured Data Management Plan (DMP); tools like RDMO are provided by the DMP4NFDI service.
- Newly derived datasets obtained at the pilot sites will be
 - published in FAIR and trusted data repository (e.g. PANGAEA)
 - with a unique and persistent identifier (e.g. DOI),
 - described with rich metadata and keywords tailored to the overarching cross-disciplinary needs,
 - using FAIR vocabularies or ontologies in a FAIR data repository.
- Datasets will address the FAIR principles F1, F2, I1, I2, R1, A1 and A2.
- Developed prototype tools will be made available as open-source on GitLab.

UC contributions and benefits

FAIRagro Connection through respective TAs and focal points	Short explanation (in bullet points)
<i>TA 1: Use Cases</i>	
UC2 - Optimal crop nitrogen management	synergies due to complementary benefit concerning cross-disciplinary usability of data products for model-validation
UC5 - Noninvasive phenotyping with robots	contribution, synergies and collaboration concerning sensor systems metadata and cross-disciplinary usability of data products; developing cross-disciplinary multimodal datasets
<i>TA 2: Community Involvement & Networking</i>	
Communication and dissemination	support is required to network with agro-community and to present the UC results to stakeholders for successful implementation (M2.1)
Training and education	collaboration with existing training programs, providing of tailored training material, joint activities in specialized workshops (M2.4)
<i>TA 3: Standardization, Interoperability & Quality</i>	
Standards for digital resources	collaboration concerning the available expertise in creation and development of an inventory of established (meta-)data standards, vocabularies and ontologies (support from M3.1)
Standards for Data Management, FAIRness and Discoverability	collaboration and contribution based on UC developments in terms of common protocols and data management plans (M3.2)
Data quality annotation and curation	contribution and collaboration in terms of the establishment of standard criteria for data quality geophysical prospecting on the basis of our pilot datasets (M3.3)
FAIR workflows and FAIR Digital Objects	utilization of the in M3.5 developed services and frameworks for describing research data workflows

<i>TA 4: Services</i>	
Central Service (‘FAIRagro Portal’)	support through the FAIRagro Infrastructure services facilitating community engagement and capacity building; central services (e.g. RDMO) are required for the implementation of UC tasks (M4.1)
Networked RDI	support, collaboration and contribution for the implementation of best practises concerning FAIR and cross-disciplinary data publications (M4.2)
Scientific Workflow Infrastructure (SciWin)	utilization of existing tools for a harmonized workflow generation (M4.4)
<i>TA5: Overarching activities</i>	
Cross-NFDI networking	support to ensure a seamless cross-consortia exchange between the involved initiatives is crucial for UC success in terms of the overall objective

UC requirements

For a successful implementation of the proposed UC, FAIRagro will play a crucial role in facilitating:

- support of a seamless cross-consortia work based on the overarching concept (in cooperation with TA5) including the provision of platforms for regular exchange and communication (in cooperation with TA2)
- support in gathering core and extended metadata entities and relevant standards that have to be considered (in cooperation with TA3)
- support in best practises for publication in cross-disciplinary relevant repositories and the findability in related metadata portals (in cooperation with TA4)

UC outcomes and outreach

Expected outcomes and impact

The UC will provide curated and quality-checked near-surface geophysical datasets with a comprehensive documentation for reanalyses and cross-disciplinary usability. With the practical implementation to demonstrate FAIR practices the UC will contribute to overcoming the four primary challenges of effective cross-domain geophysical data reuse identified by Werban et al. (2025).

Improved Data Discovery & Accessibility

- Establishment of FAIR-aligned workflows for data acquisition, processing, and publication.
- Integration of geophysical datasets into open-access repositories with standardized metadata.

Standardized Use of Public Repositories

- Development of best practices for repository use, aligning with existing infrastructures such as PANGAEA or NFDI metadata portals.
- Provision of guidelines for structured data archiving, ensuring consistency across repositories.

Harmonized Metadata Standards & Documentation

- Definition of a core and extended metadata model, integrating controlled vocabularies for sensors, methods, and soil processes.
- Development of training materials and workshops to support adoption of standardized metadata practices.

Enhanced Data Processing & Interoperability

- Implementation of standardized processing pipelines for geophysical methods such as EMI and GRS.
- Demonstration of multi-purpose data workflows at a pilot site, showcasing metadata fusion, quality control, and AI-ready data products.

Performance indicators to measure the UC success could be the number of data publications in FAIR-aligned repositories following the developed metadata model and the number of research studies relating to the UC results and datasets.

Since the overarching concept is structured across three NFDI initiatives (FAIRagro, NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Earth), there is a possibility that funding will be limited resulting in limited resources for full implementation. However, the here proposed UC will provide useful deliverables and a strategy concerning standardized data workflows and metadata models as well as FAIR-compliant datasets. This is giving guidance and insight for future near-surface geophysical applications beyond agriculture on how to enrich their metadata towards the

generation of FAIR data products. Furthermore, there is a strong requirement to align the UC with existing and future projects to integrate findings in non-funded collaborations.

Outreach & community engagement

- UC results will demonstrate the added values of the distinct implementation of the FAIR principles across several disciplines and related communities.
- Based on the practical implementation at a pilot site, engagement with researchers and practitioners will take place in an interdisciplinary working group, inviting feedback and refinements.
- UC results including best practices for interdisciplinary data sharing will be presented in workshops and specialized conferences to the targeted communities.
- UC will provide training material on data and metadata handling for all involved NFDI consortia to contribute to a culture change towards FAIR and collaborative RDM.
- UC is planned to serve as the first step in a role model for future cross-disciplinary cooperation focused on data handling and re-usability approaches and is an initial application-related cornerstone towards "oneNFDI".
- The developed workflows, metadata standards, and best practices will serve as a sustainable foundation for FAIR RDM, ensuring long-term impact through their integration into repository infrastructures, interdisciplinary collaborations, and future geophysical data initiatives - even beyond the project duration.

Workplan

Actions (Work packages)

#	Action	Responsible Institution	Contributing instit./partner
A1	<p>Development of standardised protocols and DMPs compiling core and extended metadata for the considered methods EMI, GRS and optical spectroscopy including QA/QC standards and alignment with existing geophysical metadata models (consideration and adaptation of available discipline-related geophysical standards), covering:</p> <p>1.1 Data acquisition 1.2 Data processing 1.3 Data publication and archiving</p>	UFZ	Uni Bonn (BCDH) Deutsche Bodenkundliche Gesellschaft; Deutsche Geophysikalische Gesellschaft; NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Objects
A2	<p>2.1 Development and refinement of common controlled vocabularies through a curated process ensuring compatibility with existing metadata standards in geophysics, soil science, and archaeology concerning the application-related different metadata aspects: a) sensors and instruments, b) methods, c) data structure and content, d) data processing, and e) considered phenomena and processes.</p> <p>2.2 Development of a metadata model including core and extended metadata entries (focus on a broad and cross-disciplinary applicability, ensuring interoperability with international metadata frameworks e.g., INSPIRE, ISO 19156, OGC).</p>	UFZ	Uni Bonn (BCDH) Deutsche Bodenkundliche Gesellschaft; Deutsche Geophysikalische Gesellschaft; NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Objects
A3	<p>Demonstration of FAIR implementation at an agricultural pilot site with archaeological indication to obtain multi-purpose datasets for the methods EMI, GRS and optical spectroscopy including data curation and the implementation of automated metadata compilation streamlining data documentation.</p>	UFZ	Uni Bonn (BCDH) Landesamt für Denkmalpflege und Archäologie SA
A4	<p>Outreach and capacity building</p> <p>4.1 Best practices for archiving and data publication, interfaces to metadata portals and generation of machine-readable metadata to support AI-driven geophysical data applications.</p> <p>4.2 Tailored workshops using dedicated training datasets obtained from the pilot site (including hands-on geophysical data processing and metadata structuring).</p> <p>4.3 Interfaces and collaboration with other UCs.</p>	UFZ	all partners

Milestones

#	Milestone (Name and description)	Action #	Achieved after month	x
M1	Finalized Standardized Protocols & Data Management Plan for selected methods available	1	6	
M2	First release of a harmonized metadata model and curated controlled vocabulary available	2	8	
M3	Near-surface geophysical data acquisition at agricultural pilot site completed	3	8	

Deliverables

#	Deliverable (Name and description)	Action #	Achieved after month	x
D1	Curated, quality-checked near-surface geophysical dataset package with comprehensive documentation for reanalyses and integration into archaeological prospection phase	3	10	
D2	Publication of metadata model covering core and extended metadata for selected methods in a FAIR-aligned repository	2,4	12	
D3	Provision of training material based on datasets from pilot site and presentation on a targeted workshop	4	12	